

Concept of Real-World Evidence and Real World Data in India - Overview of Current Scenario and Futuristic Perspective

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Abstract:

Real-World Evidence (RWE) and Real-World Data (RWD) have emerged as crucial components in the healthcare ecosystem, complementing traditional clinical trials and enhancing our understanding of the safety, efficacy, and effectiveness of medical products. In India, the adoption of RWE and RWD is still in its nascent stages, but the potential for their integration into the healthcare landscape is immense. This abstract explores the current state of RWE and RWD in India, highlighting the challenges and opportunities that lie ahead. It delves into the regulatory framework, data sources, and stakeholder perspectives, providing insights into the ongoing efforts to establish a robust RWE ecosystem. The growing number of regulatory frameworks and guidelines published by Competent Authorities and international initiatives that accept real-world data (RWD) sources reflects the use of real-world evidence (RWE) to support international regulatory decision-making. Real-world data (RWD) are information gathered from a wide range of sources about the health state of patients. Real-world evidence (RWE), obtained through a study of RWD, is clinical evidence about the usage and potential advantages or dangers of a medical product. It is advised that RWE studies in India concentrate on health management concerns pertinent to that nation and be carefully organized to produce high-quality data. Furthermore, the abstract presents a futuristic perspective, envisioning the potential impact of RWE and RWD on various aspects of healthcare in India. It discusses the potential benefits, such as informed decision-making, optimized resource allocation, and improved patient outcomes, while addressing the critical factors necessary for successful implementation, including data quality, interoperability, and privacy concerns. By examining the current scenario and envisioning the future, these abstract aims to serve as a foundation for further discussions and initiatives, fostering collaboration among stakeholders to harness the power of RWE and RWD in India, ultimately driving healthcare innovation and improving patient care.

Keywords:

Evidence, Quality, Rigour, Non-Communicable, Pertinent, Enormous

I. INTRODUCTION

Research on real-world evidence (RWE) has drawn attention recently and is becoming more important in determining how best to provide healthcare.^[1] RWE may contribute to a broader perspective on patient demographics and various drugs in clinical studies, as the recent COVID-19 pandemic has demonstrated.^[1] As a result, there is growing curiosity on whether non-randomized RWE can support the data from randomized controlled trials (RCTs) or support clinical decision-making. Real-world data (RWD) are information about the delivery of healthcare services and/or patient health status that is regularly gathered from several sources. Real-world evidence (RWE), obtained through a study of RWD, is clinical evidence concerning the usage and potential advantages or dangers of a medical product.^[2]

Figure 1: Representation of Real - World Data Provenance

By applying the results of clinical trials to the general population, RWE studies supplement clinical trials. Additionally, RWE can offer details on various topics, including the natural history and progression of diseases, effectiveness studies, and outcome studies.^[3] Every nation should have the correct and sufficient information about every patient, whether it is in hard copy or digital form. But as technology has advanced, paperwork has decreased significantly. Everyone now strives to maintain records digitally or electronically since technology has its advantages. However, there should be adequate and effective security of sensitive and crucial data.^[3] Because India is a more populated nation, it has always been more challenging to maintain a single, consistent data set for each patient or individual. A suitable digital patient data security policy was necessary. The central government was aware of these facts and the incidents of personal and sensitive data created a new record in the health sector and then provided a solution to these issues in the form of the public welfare act or Digital Information Security in Healthcare Act, 2018.^[4] DISHA Act is a new law in India that aims to protect digital health information and promote the use of digital technologies in healthcare. The DISHA Act also includes provisions for the use of RWE and RWD in regulatory decision-making.^[4] RWE is evidence about the safety, efficacy, and effectiveness of medical products that are generated from real-world settings, such as electronic health records (EHRs), claims data, and patient-reported outcomes (pros). RWD is the raw data that is collected from real-world settings.^[3] The DISHA Act allows the Central Drugs Standard Control Organization (CDSCO) to use RWE to support the approval of new drugs and devices and to monitor the safety of approved products. The DISHA Act also requires the CDSCO to develop and implement a framework for the use of RWE in regulatory decision-making. The use of RWE in regulatory decision-making is still in its early stages in India, but it is likely to become more common in the future. As methods for analyzing RWE and interpreting the results improve, RWE is likely to play an increasingly important role in the approval and use of medical products in India.^[4] Overall, the use of RWE in regulatory decision-making is a positive development for India. The DISHA Act and the Digital Information Security in Healthcare Act provide a strong foundation for the use of RWE in India, and the benefits of RWE are likely to outweigh the challenges. The regulation of medical equipment and drugs is currently being extensively reformed by Indian authorities. The Digital Information Security in Healthcare Act has advanced the digitalization of the healthcare system and the management of patient data, despite the absence of any specific regulations or guidelines in the area.^[4] RCTs are preliminary studies carried out to determine an experimental product's safety and effectiveness. Internal validity is the main focus of RCTs, which occasionally jeopardizes their generalizability to a larger population.^[3] Patients with comorbid conditions may

be excluded from RCTs because they are conducted on relatively specialized groups. Moreover, these investigations are carried out in highly regulated environments. The majority of clinical therapy recommendations are developed on the findings of RCTs. However, because most RCTs include a wide range of inclusion and exclusion criteria, the results do not accurately reflect the total population. As a result, to validate these RCT results, a variety of scenarios that could arise in an actual clinical setting must be considered.^[5]

TABLE 1: REAL WORLD EVIDENCE STUDY VS RANDOMIZED CLINICAL TRIALS

	RCT	RE
Types of Trial	Experimental	Observational
Primary Focus	Efficacy, safety, quality	Effectiveness
Patient Population	Narrow and restricted	Wide and unrestricted
Monitoring	Intense	Not required
Cost	High	Regularly less expensive
Randomization & Binding	Yes	No

II. ADVANTAGES OF REAL-WORLD EVIDENCE COMPARED WITH RANDOMIZED CLINICAL TRIALS^[3,5]

- Depending on the type of RWE, it may need significantly less time, resources, and money than RCT.
- In RWE research, data can be quickly accessible and easily recovered.
- RWE studies can be used to assess the prevalence, incidence, unmet medical need, existing treatment patterns, and standard of care in addition to the natural history of disease.
- RWE research can be utilized to enhance health economics and patient outcomes.
- Studies on RWE can be utilized to comprehend contemporary medical treatments.
- RWE allows for the conduct of research that RCT does not permit, such as investigations on high-risk populations.
- RWE research, as opposed to an RCT, can be used to study less common side effects.

III. SOURCES OF REAL-WORLD DATA

Health records may be kept electronically or on paper. RWD can be used if it is recorded digitally so that it can be combined and properly analyzed for study. The digitization of medical records has advanced significantly during the past 20 years.^[6] An organized collection of healthcare data that can be accessed electronically is referred to as an electronic health record (EHR). They include a variety of information, with medical records from general practitioners, specialists, or hospitals, pharmacy data, prescription data, and occasionally lifestyle-related information being the most common types.^[7] RWD is available through the following sources, as mentioned below^[8,9]

Figure 2: Sources of Real - World Data

IV. POTENTIAL BENEFITS OF REAL-WORLD EVIDENCE STUDIES ^[2,10]

- **Increased Efficiency:** RWE studies can be conducted more quickly and cheaply than clinical trials. This is because RWE data is already collected in real-world settings, such as electronic health records (EHRs), claims data, and patient-reported outcomes (pros).
- **Improved Access:** RWE studies can be used to support the approval of new drugs and devices for rare diseases and other conditions that are not well-studied in clinical trials. This can help to improve access to new treatments for patients with these conditions.
- **Enhanced Safety:** RWE studies can be used to monitor the safety of approved products over a longer period than clinical trials. This can help to identify new safety signals and to take timely action to protect patients.
- **Greater Realism:** RWE studies reflect the real-world use of medical products, which can lead to more accurate insights into safety and efficacy.
- **More Diverse Population:** RWE studies can include a wider range of patients than clinical trials, which can lead to more generalizable results.
- **Patient-Centered Focus:** RWE studies can be designed to collect data on patient-centered outcomes, such as quality of life and satisfaction with care.

V. REAL - WORLD EVIDENCE STUDIES: DESIGNS ^[10]

Retrospective and prospective designs are used in RWE investigations. Studies using a retrospective design typically cost less money and have a limited, predictable data collection period that depends on the accuracy of the clinical records that are accessible. However, the data used in these studies is often erroneous or incomplete. Such research includes, for instance:

- Hospital records
- Insurance claims
- EMRs (Electronic medical records)

Prospective design studies can provide information on long-term data on the natural history or course of the disease and can include a substantial patient data set as well as clinical data that are not typically gathered. Such studies, however, have hazy timetables that depend on how quickly qualified individuals reveal themselves and are probably expensive. Such research includes, for instance:

- Registries
- Medical studies
- Study on post-authorization safety.

VI. CHALLENGES FACED BY REAL-WORLD EVIDENCE STUDIES ^[2,10,11]

- **Data Quality:** RWE data can be noisy and incomplete. This can be due to several factors, such as the way the data is collected, the quality of the data collection tools, and the lack of standardization in data collection methods.
- **Bias:** RWE studies can be biased if the data is not collected or analyzed carefully. This can occur, for example, if the study population is not representative of the general population, or if the data is not adjusted for confounding factors.
- **Interpretability:** It can be difficult to interpret the results of RWE studies because they are often observational, rather than experimental. This means that the results of RWE studies cannot be used to establish causality.
- **Regulatory Acceptance:** RWE is still a relatively new concept in regulatory decision-making. As a result, there is not yet a clear consensus on how RWE should be used to support regulatory approvals.
- **Cost:** RWE studies can be expensive to conduct, especially if they involve large datasets or complex analytical methods.
- **Privacy And Security:** RWE studies often involve the use of sensitive patient data. It is important to take steps to protect the privacy and security of this data.
- **Transparency:** It can be difficult to ensure transparency in RWE studies, as the data sources may be proprietary or difficult to access.

VII. REAL-WORLD EVIDENCE STUDY: PLANNING

Planning a Real-world study should take into account several elements, including design, conduct, monitoring, quality, ethics, reporting, safety, etc. ^[10,11]

For instance, the design of an RWE study registry is based on the following factors: - ^[10,11]

- **Defining The Research Question:** The first step is to clearly define the research question that the RWE study will address. This will help to determine the type of data that needs to be collected and the analytical methods that will be used.
- **Identifying The Data Sources:** RWE studies can use a variety of data sources, such as electronic health records (EHRS), claims data, and patient-reported outcomes (pros). The specific data sources that are used will depend on the research question that is being addressed.
- **Developing The Study Design:** The study design will determine how the data will be collected and analyzed. RWE studies can use a variety of study designs, such as cohort studies, case-control studies, and time-to-event studies.
- **Providing For Data Quality Assurance:** It is important to ensure that the data that is used in the RWE study is of high quality. This can be done by developing data cleaning and validation procedures.
- **Analyzing The Data:** The data will be analyzed using statistical methods to answer the research question.
- **Interpreting The Results:** The results of the RWE study will be interpreted in light of the research question and the study design.
- **Communicating The Results:** The results of the RWE study will be communicated to stakeholders, such as patients, healthcare professionals, and policymakers.

VIII. CONDUCT OF REAL-WORLD EVIDENCE STUDY

Like any clinical trial, the RWE study must be approved by the ethics committee before it can proceed. Potential participants must also give their informed consent before their identifiable medical records may be accessed for research, whether it be interventional or non-interventional. Data integrity must be guaranteed by well-trained site personnel, a risk-based monitoring approach, and medical monitoring. Consent processes, randomization integrity, safety, and thorough follow-up should all be monitored on the site ^[11,12]

Figure 3: Flow chart of Conduct of Real -World Evidence Study

IX. QUALITY OF REAL-WORLD EVIDENCE STUDY

Quality assurance of data, computerized systems have confidence that the design, conduct, and analysis of the registry could guard against bias (systematic error) and errors in inference, that is, erroneous conclusions drawn from a study, quality assurance of data, data collection/registry procedures, and computerized systems are essential.^[13] Focusing on external validity, internal validity, analysis, and reporting is crucial for RWE studies, especially for registries.

External validity relies on demonstrating that registry members closely resembled the intended group, that selection bias was minimized, and that the evaluation and description of the completeness of data on eligible patients.^[11] To ensure internal validity, it is required to gather the pertinent data for important exposures, risk factors, and particular exposure data to support the major research questions. Additionally, data checks and consistency checks must be performed. Additionally, a clear and precise method of asking about complaints or negative incidents is essential for safety registry studies.

Analysis and reporting include a thorough explanation of the methods, the reporting of results for all primary objectives, the use of accepted analytical techniques, a description of the follow-up period to enable assessment of the impact of the observation period on the conclusions, consideration of the impact of missing data and confounding variables, clarity in the conclusions drawn and the implications of the study's findings, and consistency in comparison of results with those from other pertinent researches.

X. REAL-WORLD EVIDENCE STUDIES IN INDIA ^[3]

The use of real-world evidence (RWE) studies in India is still in its early stages, but it is growing rapidly. There are several factors driving the growth of RWE studies in India, including:

- The increasing availability of electronic health records (EHRs) and other large-scale data sources.
- The growing recognition of the value of RWE by regulatory agencies and healthcare stakeholders.
- The development of new analytical methods that can be used to extract meaningful insights from RWE data.

Figure 4: Process of Real-World Evidence Studies in India ^[3,4]

Several RWE studies have been conducted in India in recent years, covering a wide range of topics, including:

- The safety and efficacy of new drugs and devices.
- The effectiveness of existing treatments for chronic diseases.
- The cost-effectiveness of medical products and services.
- The impact of healthcare policies and interventions on patient outcomes.

For example, one RWE study conducted in India found that a new drug for the treatment of diabetes was safe and effective in reducing blood sugar levels in patients with type 2 diabetes. Another RWE study found that a new surgical procedure for the treatment of heart disease was more effective than the standard treatment in reducing mortality rates.

The use of RWE studies in India is likely to continue to grow in the coming years. This is because RWE studies offer several advantages over traditional clinical trials, such as:

- RWE studies can be conducted more quickly and cheaply than clinical trials.
- RWE studies can be conducted in real-world settings, which makes them more representative of the general population.
- RWE studies can collect data on a wider range of outcomes, including patient-reported outcomes.

As the use of RWE studies in India grows, it is important to ensure that these studies are conducted rigorously and transparently. This will help to ensure that the results of RWE studies are credible and can be used to inform informed healthcare decision-making.

Here are some specific examples of RWE studies that are being conducted in India:

- The Indian Council of Medical Research (ICMR) is conducting several RWE studies to evaluate the effectiveness of existing treatments for chronic diseases, such as diabetes, heart disease, and cancer.
- The National Health Authority (NHA) is conducting several RWE studies to evaluate the cost-effectiveness of medical products and services.
- The Drugs Controller General of India (DCGI) is developing guidance on the use of RWE in regulatory decision-making.

The growing use of RWE studies in India is a positive development. RWE studies can help to improve the safety, efficacy, and accessibility of medical products and services. They can also help to inform healthcare policy and practice.

XI. MYTHS OF REAL-WORLD EVIDENCE STUDIES IN INDIA

RWE studies are not required in India by insurance companies or authorities. Therefore, these studies are typically carried out by pharmaceutical corporations on a pricey new medication. These trials involve consenting individuals who have been prescribed a new drug for a sufficient amount of time and who match the selection criteria. Bases for determining sample size are efficacy endpoints. The sponsor monitors the quality of the data regularly. Some of the RWE studies funded by pharmaceutical companies gather information on treatment-related efficacy endpoints through cross-sectional surveys. As the prescribers are in a private clinic or hospital setting, whose patients can afford the expense of therapy and investigations, such studies suffer from selection bias. Such studies' findings confirm premarket effectiveness findings.

Investigator-initiated observational studies and disease registries are other examples of RWE. These studies record disease prevalence and features but frequently provide scant information on patient characteristics, therapies, history of disease, and long-term outcomes.

XII. CURRENT SCENARIO OF REAL-WORLD EVIDENCE IN INDIA ^[14]

Hospitals spend a lot of time and effort recording patient data. In India, there is no legal structure or set of regulations that would make it possible to gather information from hospitals on common measures of the effectiveness of patient care. This can be one of the causes of the poor quality of medical records. Many hospitals don't even keep detailed records of patients' medical histories, and the information they do keep is sometimes very little. Compared to state hospitals, the hospitals in the private sector have more funding and resources. However, it is not necessary to get this data because there are no laws requiring it. Public hospitals are also overrun with patients. For RWD, clearly defined formats in the doctor's office are necessary to produce data that can be properly analyzed.

XIII. WHAT CAN BE DONE NEXT?

It is essential to design quick and simple computer-readable formats for data collection at the clinic or hospital to provide RWD.^[14]

India has an advantage in conducting RWE studies because of its diversified and large population, notably in the following areas: - ^[3]

- The natural history and long-term effects of noncommunicable diseases like diabetes, hypertension, and heart failure as well as communicable diseases like drug-resistant tuberculosis.
- Government hospitals' health economics and outcomes studies in comparison to commercial institutions
- Identifying unmet medical issues that are important to the Indian people
- Comparative efficacy studies between branded and generic products and between biologic and biosimilar products
- A comparison of the effectiveness of Indian prescription dosage and prescribing data.

The following must be carried out for RWE studies to be conceived, carried out, analyzed, and reported effectively in India: -

- It would be necessary for several stakeholders, including the government, academics, researchers, the pharmaceutical business, and patient support groups, to collaborate and promote the conduct of RWE studies that are pertinent to Indian healthcare.
- It is necessary to create RWE guidelines relevant to India.
- Support for public and private hospitals in the areas of data management, statisticians, and technical assistance to assist them in creating structured formats for data collection as well as in correctly analyzing and summarizing RWE research.

XIV. CONCLUSION

Real-world evidence (RWE) and real-world data (RWD) are rapidly emerging as important tools for medical research and decision-making. RWE is the evidence that is generated from the analysis of RWD. RWE has the potential to address some of the limitations of traditional clinical trials, such as their high cost, and time-consuming nature. RWE can be used to generate evidence on a variety of topics, including the efficacy and safety of drugs and medical devices, the effectiveness of clinical guidelines, and the impact of healthcare interventions on patient outcomes. However, there are also some challenges associated with the use of RWE. One challenge is that RWD can be complex and heterogeneous, and it can be difficult to ensure that it is of high quality and representative of the population of interest. Another challenge is that RWE studies often require sophisticated statistical methods to analyze the data. Despite these challenges, the potential benefits of RWE are significant. RWE can help to improve the efficiency and effectiveness of medical research and decision-making, and it can lead to better patient care.

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